

to 76% (see table). In a second observation of three promising lines, yield losses ranged from 66 to 83% and ragged stunt infection ranged from 34 to 74%.

The observations indicate that the disease has the potential to cause severe losses. Further research is needed to identify resistant sources that can be incorporated into commercial varieties. ❧

Occurrence of ufra disease in transplanted rice

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Ufra disease of rice, caused by *Ditylenchus angustus*, had occurred only in deepwater rice in Bangladesh since Butler first reported it in 1913. During the 1977 aman season, however, ufra was found in transplanted aman rice on the BRRI farm, Joydebpur. The disease appeared in only one experimental field and affected four rice varieties. IR20, Nizersail, and BR4 were severely infested with 70, 80, and 90% affected tillers, respectively. Severe stunting, incomplete panicle emergence, and brown discoloration of boot and flag-leaf bases were observed. The occurrence disproves the previous observation that ufra disease is confined to deepwater rice. Under favorable conditions it may affect other rice crops. ❧

Monthly fluctuation in number of conidia of rice blast fungus trapped by spore sampler

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In 1976 and 1977, a disease nursery was established for epidemiologic studies of rice blast in the field in the first and second rice crops. The rice varieties Tainan 5 (moderately resistant to neck blast) and Chianon shen 8 (susceptible) were grown at a 20- × 25-cm spacing in four equal plots of 6 × 8 m divided by

crossing lines. The varieties were alternated; each variety occupied two nonadjoining plots. The experimental field was given a standard fertilizer treatment — 120-60-50kg/ha of N, P₂O₅, and K₂O, respectively. An automatic Kramar-Collins spore sampler was placed at the center of the experimental field to collect conidia the year round. Samples were taken 4 times/hour for a total of 6 minutes; the total air volume was 120 liters. The first crop was transplanted in late January and harvested in early June; the second crop was transplanted in late July and harvested in early November.

In both years, the number of trapped conidia was highest in April and August, in the first and second crops (see table). The peaks in trapped conidia coincided with the peaks of leaf blast in 1976 and 1977. But no conidia were trapped in

Number of conidia of rice blast fungus trapped monthly in 1976 and 1977 in the field. Chia-yi Agricultural Experiment Station, Taiwan.

Month	Conidia (no.) trapped in	
	1976	1977
January	0	0
February	0	0
March	651	13
April	4,544	818
May	695	162
June	111	19
July	43	103
August	749	497
September	45	303
October	39	15
November	14	0
December	0	0

January, February, or November 1977, or in December of 1976 or 1977. That probably indicates that the rice blast fungus overwintered for 3 to 4 months in Taiwan. ❧

Pest management and control

INSECTS

Brachmia arotrae, a leaf folder of rice in India

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Caterpillars of *Brachmia arotrae* sp. were observed folding and damaging rice leaves at the Central Rice Research Institute farm, Cuttack, in November and December 1977. The adult is smaller than *C. medinalis* and pale straw in color. Eggs are light yellow, flat, and oval, laid singly on the leaves or, occasionally, in rows. The incubation period is 4 to 5 days. The fully grown larva has a black head and prothoracic shield and is about 10 mm long. It folds the leaves and feeds on the epidermis from inside the folded leaf. About a month is required to complete one generation. The pest, along with *C. medinalis*, was abundant in late-planted crops and accounted for 30 to 40% of the leaf folder population during the first week of December at Cuttack. Both *C. medinalis* and

B. arotrae were also found infesting the weed *Leersia hexandra*. *C. medinalis* and *B. arotrae* were found to be parasitized by *Apanteles* sp. and *Brachmeria* sp.

Brachmia arotrae is becoming increasingly important. It was also observed in certain parts of Madurai district of Tamil Nadu; it may now be fairly well distributed in India. It appears to have missed the attention of rice researchers in India, perhaps because its damage closely resembles that from *C. medinalis*. ❧

Nematodes in paddy fields of Pakistan

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Nematodes damage the paddy crop in many rice-growing areas of the world. Nematode species found in Pakistan are *Aphelenchoides* sp., *Criconeoides* sp., *Ditylenchus* sp., *Helicotylenchus*